

1 CHASERR is a CHD2-associated non-coding RNA perturbed during imprinting-type transformation.

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7 We demonstrate here functional contribution of a non-coding RNA encoded adjacent to CHD2,
8 *CHASERR*, to transformation in humans. Imprinting-type transcriptional activity involving Xist likely plays a
9 dominant and broad role in transformation.

10 Citations

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15 Ulitsky, I., 2019. Regulation of CHD2 expression by the Chaserr long noncoding RNA gene is essential for
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Results

1. *CHASERR* is silenced by KRas G12V expression.

GSE120566

2. Expression of a Polybromo-1 point mutant results in activation of *CHASERR*.

GSE149874

3. *CHASERR* is among the genes most abundantly activated in human leukemias induced by the MLL-AF9 fusion oncogene.

GSE244470

n=2 wildtype HSPC vs n=2 MLL-AF9 AML